

SEMANTIC ANALYSIS OF LEXICAL UNITS EXPRESSING HUMAN EMOTIONAL STATE

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Abstract.

The Purpose Of This Scientific Article Is To Analyze The Semantic Properties Of Lexical Units That Express A Person's Emotional State, Determine Their Place In The System Of Language Units, Divide Them Into Semantic Groups, And Classify Them Based On Practical Analysis. The Topic Of This Article Is One Of The Current Issues In Linguistics. It Is Also Mentioned That Words Expressing Emotional States Are A Complex And Multifaceted Manifestation Of The Semantic Layers Of The Language, And That Words Contain Connotative, Stylistic, Associative And Cultural Meanings. Therefore, By Analyzing Them In Depth, It Is Possible To Determine Not Only The Lexical Meaning Of Linguistic Units, But Also The Emotional Content They Express.

Key Words: Semantics, Emotional Lexicon, Translation, Emotional State, Idiom, Collocation, Context.

Аннотация.

Целью Данной Научной Статьи Является Анализ Семантических Свойств Лексических Единиц, Выражающих Эмоциональное Состояние Человека, Определение Их Места В Системе Языковых Единиц, Разделение Их На Семантические Группы И Классификация На Основе Практического Анализа. Тема Данной Статьи — Одна Из Актуальных Проблем Языкознания. Также Было Отмечено, Что Слова, Выражающие Эмоциональные Состояния, Представляют Собой Сложное И Многогранное Отражение Семантических Пластов Языка, И Что Слова Содержат Коннотативные, Стилистические, Ассоциативные И Культурные Значения. Поэтому, Углубленно Анализируя Их, Можно Определить Не Только Лексическое Значение Языковых Единиц, Но И Выражаемое Ими Эмоциональное Содержание.

Ключевые Слова: Семантика, Эмоциональная Лексика, Перевод, Эмоциональное Состояние, Идиома, Словосочетание, Контекст.

Annotatsiya.

Ushbu Ilmiy Maqolaning Maqsadi – Shaxsning Emotsional Holatini Ifodalovchi Leksik Birliklarning Semantik Xususiyatlarini Tahlil Qilishdan Hamda Ularning Til Birliklari Tizimidagi O‘Rnini Aniqlash, Semantik Guruhlarga Bo‘Lish Va Amaliy Tahlil Asosida Tasniflashdan Iborat. Ushbu Maqolaning Mavzusi Tilshunoslik Fanining Dolzarb Masalalaridan Biridir. Shuningdek, Emotsional Holatni Ifodalovchi So‘Zlar Tilning Semantik Qatlamlarining Murakkab Va Ko‘P Qirrali Ko‘Rinishi, So‘Zlarning Konnotativ, Stilistik, Assotsiativ Va Madaniy Ma‘nolarni O‘Z Ichiga Olishi Haqida Aytib O‘Tilgan. Shuning Uchun Ularni Chuqur Tahlil Qilish Orqali Til Birliklarining Nafaqat Leksik Ma‘nosini, Balki U Ifodalagan Emotsional Mazmunini Ham Aniqlash Mumkin.

Kalit So‘Zlar: Semantika, Emotsional Leksika, Tarjima, Emotsional Holat, Idioma, Birikma, Kontekst.

Introduction

In Today's Era Of Globalization, The Role Of Lexical Units In Expressing Human Psychology, His Emotional State, Inner World And Spiritual Experiences Through Language Is Extremely Important. Emotionally Expressive Words In The Language Serve To Accurately Convey A Person's Spiritual Experiences, Thoughts And Feelings. Emotionally Expressive Words In The Language Serve To Accurately Convey A Person's Spiritual Experiences, Thoughts And Feelings. With The Help Of These Words, A Person Can Express His State, Feelings, And Life Experience. Therefore, The Semantic Analysis Of Lexical Units Expressing An Emotional State Is Of Great Importance Not Only In Linguistics, But Also In The Fields Of Psychology, Cultural Studies, Translation And Communication.

Emotional Lexical Units Are Language Units That Express Human Emotions And Play An Important Role In Transmitting Them. This Article Analyzes The Semantic Properties Of Emotional Lexical Units In English, Their Functional Role, And The Main Problems In The Process Of Translating Them Into Uzbek. The Purpose Of This Graduation Qualification Work Is To Analyze The Semantic Properties Of Lexical Units Expressing A Person's Emotional State, Determine Their Place In The System Of Language Units, Divide Them Into Semantic Groups And Classify Them Based On Practical Analysis. This Work Aims To Implement The Following Tasks:

- Identify The Main Lexical Units Expressing An Emotional State;
 - Analyze Their Semantic Properties;
 - Show Synonym, Antonym And Connotation Relationships;
- Study The Use Of Emotional Units Based On Practical Texts;

Draw Conclusions Based On The Results Of The Analysis.

Lexical Units Expressing An Emotional State In The English Language Were Taken As The Object Of Research.

Main Part

The Subject Of The Research Is The Semantic Properties Of These Units, Their Synonym-Antonymic Relationships, Connotations And Semantic Loading In The Context. The Graduation Thesis Consists Of An Introduction, Three Main Chapters, A Conclusion, And A List Of References. Lexicography Is A Branch Of Lexicology, Which Deals With Compiling Of Dictionaries. English Lexicography As A Prescriptive Science Began With Publication In 1755 Of Samuel Johnson's "Dictionary Of The English Language In Which The Words Are Deduced From Their Originals And Illustrated In Their Different Significations By Examples From The Best Writers". The Influence Of This Two-Volume Book Was So Great That In 1880 A Bill Was Thrown Out Of The Parliament Because A Word In It Was Not In "The Dictionary", As S. Johnson's Dictionary Was Named. S. Johnson Became A Linguistic Legislator: He Fixed The Spellings Of Many Disputed Words, Revised Some Etymologies And Exhibited The Vocabulary Of English More Fully Than Before. It Is Still Referred To As "The Dictionary" And The Bookstores Know It Under This Name, Just Like What Is Meant As "The Bible" Or "The Prayer Book". It Had 2500 Pages And Included 40 000 Glosses/Entries. History Of English Lexicography Starts With "Epinal Glossary" From 7 Th century (Epinal Is A French City Where The Only Copy Of This Glossary Was Found). It Has Definitions Of Difficult Latin And Old English Words. The First English-Latin Dictionary Was Compiled By A Monk Galfrid From Norfolk In 1440 Including Translation Of 10 000 English Words Into Latin. There Are 4 Periods In English Lexicography: 1/Glossarization (Description Of Lexicon) 2/Description Of "Difficult Words" 3/Prescriptive (Normative) 4/ Scientific (Lexicon As A System - Roget's Thesaurus)/ The Most Authoritative English Dictionary Is "A New English Dictionary On Historical Principles (1858 - 1928), Known As Oxford English Dictionary, Including 12 Volumes (In 1933 - Volume 13 With New Words Was Issued). It Comprises 414 000 Lexical Units, Illustrated With 1 827 306 Citations, Selected From 6 Million References, And Includes Words From 1150 In Their Historical Development. American Lexicography Started With Publication Of Samuel Johnson's 5 (Namesake Of Samuel Johnson From Great Britain) "A School Dictionary" In 1789. Other Dictionaries Followed Mainly Describing Differences In The New World Lexicon. The Most Authoritative American Dictionary Is Noah Webster's "An American Dictionary Of The English Language"

(1806) Published In 1828, Including 70 000 Entries. "Look Up Webster" Is A Popular Phrase In US When It Comes To Consulting A Dictionary. The Problems Of Lexicography Are Numerous. They Are: 1) The Selection Of Items For Inclusion And Their Arrangement; 2) The Setting Of The Entries; 3) The Selection, Arrangement And Definition Of Meanings; 4) The Illustrative Examples To Be Supplied; 5) The Supplementary Material. The Choice Among The Possible Solution Of These Problems Depends Upon The Type Of The Dictionary, The Aims Of The Compiler And The Users Of The Dictionaries.

The Word Semantics Comes From The Greek Word "Semainein" - "To Designate, Express", And In Linguistics It Studies The Meaning Of Words. Emotional Lexicon Includes Words That Express Emotional States, Moods, And Relationships.

Linguistic Characteristics Of Emotional Vocabulary

Emotional Words Have Special Phonetic, Morphological, And Syntactic Characteristics. For Example, The Phrase "Oh My God!" Carries An Emotional Charge Not Only Semantically, But Also Intonationally.

Conclusion

Emotional Lexical Units Are Semantically Complex And One Of The Most Difficult Areas To Translate. When Translating Them Into Uzbek, It Is Necessary To Take Into Account The Context, Cultural Differences And Semantic Depths. Also, The Translator Must Understand The Language Not Only In Linguistic, But Also In Cultural Context.

Analysis And Results

Types Of Emotional Lexical Units And Their Functions

These Units Are Divided Into:

- Verbs Expressing Emotional States (E.G., Love, Hate, Admire)
- Evaluative Adjectives (E.G., Horrible, Wonderful, Disgusting)
- Exclamatory Phrases (E.G., What A Surprise!)

Such Words Often Have Connotative Meanings, And Their Misinterpretation Can Create Ambiguity In Communication.

Emotional Sentences

Sentences Such As "Why On Earth Would You Do That?" Are Semantically Interrogative, But In Reality Express Surprise, Anger, Or Astonishment.

Emotional Words In Idioms And Collocations

Emotional Idioms (E.G., "To Be Over The Moon") Are Common In English, And Their Direct Translation Does Not Always Make Sense.

Translating Emotional Vocabulary Into Uzbek

The Role Of Context In Translation

Context Is A Key Factor In Correctly Interpreting The Meaning Of Emotional Units².

Common Problems In Translation

- Lack Of Equivalent (E.G., The Word “Cringe” Has No Clear Equivalent In Uzbek)
- Cultural Connotations (E.G., The Meaning Of The Phrase “Bless Your Heart” In An Ironic Context)

Lexical Semantics And Semantic Structure Of The Word Based On The Lexicon

Each Emotional Unit Has A Semantic Core And Peripheral Elements. This Analysis Is Important In The Translation Process

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